

Management and Enforcement of Secured E2E Network Slices across Transport Domains

Pol Alemany^a, Alejandro Molina^b, Cyril Dangerville^c, Rodrigo Asensio^b, Dhouha Ayed^c, Raul Muñoz^a, Ramon Casellas^a, Ricardo Martínez^a, Antonio Skarmeta^b, Ricard Vilalta^a

^aCentre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Carl Friedrich Gauss Av. 7, Castelldefels, 08860, Catalonia, Spain

^bUniversidad de Murcia., Computer Science Faculty, Campus de Espinardo, Murcia, 30100, Murcia, Spain

^cThales, 1 av. Augustin Fresnel, 91120, Palaiseau, Essonne, France

Abstract

Due to the fact that the current variability of services is brought by the current networks and the new possibilities that will appear thanks to the near-future networks, Network Slicing has become one of the key elements to allow the co-existence of multiple computing and transport services with different requirements (i.e., performance, security, isolation) over the same infrastructure in multi-tenant and multi-domain (i.e., edge, transport, core) scenarios. The use of this and other technologies allow to have only one generic infrastructure (e.g., an optical transport domain) despite the services differences, instead of needing specific resources (e.g., on single optical fiber) for each type of service. Multiple works have been published about Network Slicing, Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks using multiple computing and transport domains but, based on our literature research, there is one important aspect with a low amount of attention: the security management around network slices and their enforcement. It is essential to ensure that the expected Quality of Security (QoSec) is accomplished based on the correct deployment and posterior monitoring of the security metrics defined in the agreed Security Service Level Agreement (SSLA) between the service requester and the provider.

This article aims to present an architecture designed to manage and control the life-cycle of secured End-to-End (E2E) network slices involving multiple domains based on the SSLA requirements. The security management architecture is described with its components together with the deployment and monitoring processes and the data objects used. Finally, an experimental validation is described using the use case of a DoS attack scenario and its resolution.

Keywords: Network Slicing, Security Service Level Agreement, Network Function Virtualisation, Quality of Service

1. Introduction

In the last years, the network management and control has shifted from individual domains controlled by specific players towards a scenario in which all domains work together to create a single service entity despite still being owned by different players. This new scenario became possible due to the fact of using Software-Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies. For example, the configuration of multiple optical connectivity services with different spectrum requirements or the idea of configuring a black box as a router or switch according to the needs. Because of the co-existence of the NFV and SDN technologies, it became possible to increase the capabilities and performance not only of the transport domain resources but also on the edge and core domain

resources with the creation of network slices [1].

Network slicing is not only about deploying a set of computing resources in two different domains but also interconnecting them in order to compose a full virtual dedicated network for the service offered by those computing resources. So, (packet-optical) transport domains are an absolute need as they grant that the information is exchanged through the configuration and deployment of connectivity services. Said this, an End-to-End (E2E) Network Slice in multi-domain scenarios (i.e., RAN, Transport and Core as in Fig.1) follows the idea defined by the ETSI (and the 3GPP before) in [2] where a network slice is composed of "slice-subnets". Each slice-subnet is a set of resources available in each domain, such as a dedicated optical fiber (i.e., hard isolation) or the configuration of a Transport-API (T-API) [3] connectivity service (i.e., soft isolation) in a packet-

optical transport domain. While these examples allow to create secure transport slice-subnets, their management should not be done individually, but in synchronization, with the computing resources deployment and security management of the other slice-subnets that compose an E2E Network Slice as a whole.

As it happens with any new element/technology, the security around it is a key aspect that needs to be studied and researched in order to keep evolving and improving its usage on the management and control of optical resources infrastructures. Security aspects on Network Slicing were defined in [4] with emphasis on isolation or the use of Service Level Agreements (SLAs). As described by A. Marotta et al. [5][6] isolation may have multiple shapes, from having a specific optical fiber dedicated to each slice to share an optical fiber with multiple virtual links, each per slice. Despite the first case is the most secured option, it is also not easily feasible in terms of transport resources management as it implies an optical fiber per network slice. The second option, improves the management of transport domain resources but forces the different network slices to co-exist using virtual links. Because of this co-existence, it is necessary to implement SLAs focused on security aspects for the multiple elements composing network slices. There is plenty of work within the networks community studying the relationship between Network Slicing and SLAs. For example, Assis et al. [7] presented a new methodology that efficiently designs network slices based on the SLA demands focusing especially on the route and spectrum allocation requirements. Xue et al.[8] demonstrated with interesting results the reconfiguration of Optical Data Centers participating in a network slice, based on Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. Chen et al. [9] uses spectral network layer together with Network Slicing resource allocation to deploy the requested service with the expected QoS under an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) environment. Taking the literature citations presented as an example, an important gap was detected in the relationship between Network Slicing and Security SLAs (SSLAs). So, to the best of our knowledge, this article aims to present one of the first architectures focused on the security aspects management around Networks Slices in a multi-domain scenario.

While previous work [10] was focused on the enforcement and monitoring of SSLAs to ensure the QoS of the services deployed in a network slice, the main novelty of this article is on the security management and monitoring around the deployed network slice using a more complete architecture that aims to keep the inde-

pendence of each domain while allowing them to work all together from an E2E point of view. Moreover, this article improves the description of the architecture initially presented in [11] by presenting more details and a better vision of how its components work together and by adding a new security use case and validation in relation to the one presented in [12].

To do so, the complete process is described: first of all with the elements to deploy and configure the E2E network slices and the SSLAs associated, then with the main management actions (i.e., E2E secured network slice deployment and monitoring) and the data objects used to apply the different actions and finally with an experimental validation using an emulated Denial of Service (DoS) attack environment and its SSLA resolution.

The rest of this article is structured into the following sections. Section 2 illustrates the generic architecture to deploy secured E2E network slices and monitor them based on associated SSLAs. Section 3 presents the experimental validation, the results obtained with the implemented use case and a discussion related to them. Finally, the conclusions and future work are presented in section 4.

2. Security Configuration and Management for Network Slices

This section aims to present the designed architecture to apply and monitor the security aspects around network slices and their internal Network Services (NSs). Moreover, the workflows about how a secured E2E network slice is deployed and its monitoring process to detect and solve any SSLA violation are described. Finally, an overview of the data objects involved in the deployment of the secured E2E network slices is presented.

2.1. A Generic Architecture to Manage Network Slices and Their Security

The architecture is illustrated in Fig.1 and it is composed of three main layers; (i) the E2E Security Management Domain (SMD), (ii) the Security Management Domains and (iii) the Physical Infrastructure.

2.1.1. E2E Security Management Domain

The E2E SMD, as the layer on top, includes the modules in charge of ensuring that the overall E2E point of view is correctly implemented using the correct composition of available resources alongside multiple SMDs. The modules at this layer will act either when a new action needs to be implemented (i.e., architecture entry

Figure 1: Architecture design for managing secured network slices.

point) or when an action that happened in one SMD may affect another SMD. The elements involved in the E2E SMD are:

- **E2E Network Slice Manager (Mngr):** This module has the responsibility to manage any action during the life-cycle of E2E network slices and their slice-subnets. A slice-subnet may be a single pre-defined NS with its Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) and Virtual Security Functions (VSFs) or another network slice (and its NSs). A VSF is a security-dedicated element (i.e., vFirewall, virtual Intrusion Detection System (vIDS)) deployed next to the VNFs with the objective to protect the VNFs while these offer the expected service to the final user. Each of these elements is deployed through the corresponding Slicing & NFV/SDN Infrastructure SMD. Due to the fact that these elements are pre-defined, Network Slicing makes use of a data object called Network Slice Templates (NSTs). Each NST defines a set of slice-subnets and how they are linked among them in order to have the final deployed service. As an NST is a pre-defined element, for each deployment based on an NST, a new data object called Network Slice Instance (NSI) is created. Each NSI makes reference to its NST and keeps the specific information of the deployed resources (e.g., connectivity services in transport domains, computing resources in the edge or cloud domains, etc.).
- **E2E SSLA Mngr:** This module is in charge of defining and managing the SSLA objects which, similarly to the NSTs, need to be defined and stored in the SSLA Mngr. The main functionality of the SSLA Mngr is the correct selection of the SSLA based on the requested NST and the security

requirements desired for the resulting NSI. Moreover, once the best SSLA is selected, the SSLA Mngr has to take into account and inform about the singularities of each domain (defined in the NST) that might participate in the secured E2E network slice by decomposing the E2E requirements into specific domain requirements.

- **E2E Security Orchestrator (SO):** This module takes care of managing the different actions required from the E2E point of view to the specific domain point of view. While the previous two modules managed NST/NSIs and SSLAs, the E2E SO deals with the policies to either deploy the network slice elements (i.e., NSs and SFs) or to configure the monitoring system based on the SSLA. To do so, the E2E SO receives a Medium-level Security Policy Language (MSPL) data object from the E2E Network Slice Manager that defines which elements and where (i.e., SMD) are they deployed. Then, the E2E SO will translate the received MSPL into specific multiple MSPLs, one per each SMD SO involved. Finally, each involved SMD SO will translate the received MSPL to the corresponding SMD NST deployment request.
- **E2E Policy Framework (PF):** This module contains a set of pre-defined set of policies ready to be applied when required. The E2E PF takes care of detecting if there is a conflict between a policy to be applied and those already applied at the E2E level. For example, if a violated SSLA resolution involves actions in multiple SMDs, the E2E PF verifies that the selected policy in one SMD can be applied equally in another SMD without causing new problems.
- **E2E Data Services:** This module is the component where all the previous modules store their data, keeping it ready to be accessed and ensuring that the right data model is respected for each data object (i.e., NSTs/NSIs, SSLA, policies, etc.). The reasons to centralize the information are: a) in case of a failure in a module, the data is protected and not lost and b) as the data stored contains critical information of different domains such as computing and transport resources, there is one unique access to it and so, it is easier to verify "who or what" aims to access it. Only authorized consumers may access this module. Because of this element, data persistence and data processing are divided which allows stateless management functions.

2.1.2. Single Management Domain

Below the E2E SMD, there might be as many SMDs as needed. Keeping in mind that an NST at the SMD level is a slice-subnet at the E2E SMD level, the co-existence of multiple SMDs with specific NSTs based on each domain characteristics and resources allows the E2E SMD to offer a wide variety of E2E secured network slices with the best Quality of Security (QoSec) possible in each SMD. Regarding the control architecture at a domain layer, a similar approach than in the E2E is designed with some similar modules with limited range of action within its domain:

- **Security Orchestrator:** This module takes care of receiving and managing the policy deployment from the E2E SO regarding the slice-subnet in its domain. Based on the policy requests coming from the E2E SO, it applies the following internal actions: a) analyzes the policy requirements to generate an orchestration plan based on them, b) it requests the slice-subnet to the Network Slice Mngr/MANO element and, c) makes sure to apply the security configuration according to the orchestration plan to enforce the expected QoSec. To do this last step, it uses the Decision Engine and the Analytics Engine & Data Collector modules to configure the monitoring elements using the required metrics.
- **Policy Framework:** Similarly to its "parent" module in the E2E SMD, the PF in each SMD assists the SO with associated final infrastructure configurations associated to the security policies in the orchestration process and it also contains the policies defining the possible actions (i.e., re-deployment, re-configuration, isolation, etc.) to be applied when an SSLA violation is detected.
- **Analytics Engine & Data Collector (AE/DC):** This module receives the expected monitored data from multiple elements deployed within the slice-subnet resources (i.e., monitoring agents, SFs, NSs, etc.) in order to collect the data, analyse the metrics and process them to generate the final data samples sent to the DE for the final decision on SSLA violation remediation.
- **Decision Engine (DE):** While the SO is the main element on the security deployment, the DE is the key element on enforcing the resolution of SSLA violations over the deployed slice-subnet. When a service is deployed, the DE receives the metrics and SLOs related to the selected SSLA and passes the metrics to collect to the AE/DC. Then, while

the service monitoring process is alive, the DE receives a set of monitored and analyzed data and decides whether an SSLA in that domain has been violated and second, which is the best solution to remediate an SSLA violation. To select the best solution, the DE requests the policies associated with the SSLA (or the specific violated metric) from the PF and maps the selected policy into a specific action to be applied.

- **Slicing & NFV/SDN Infrastructure:** This module contains the Network Slice Mngr/MANO and the rest of the NFV architecture [13] that manages the life-cycle of the E2E slice-subnets such as the domain NST/NSIs, the SFs and the NSs. This module is composed of a Network Slice Mngr on top, then, right below, the Management and Orchestration (MANO) module with the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) -i.e., NFV- and the WAN Infrastructure Manager (WIM) -i.e., SDN-elements. While first element manages the computing resources (i.e., the NSs and SFs) the second element makes reference to the transport (packet-optical) SDN controller that takes care to configure and manage all the actions over the packet-optical transport resources.
- **Data Services:** A similar concept than the E2E Data Service, in terms of characteristics is the same but the information stored is different. For example, the NSTs stored in each Domain may be composed by other NSTs or NSs available in the same domain, but the E2E NSTs stored at the E2E Data Services are composed only by NSTs available in the multiple SMDs. So, when an E2E NST is selected, the corresponding SMD NSTs will be requested. For the other data objects, the same model is followed, so an E2E element is composed of SMDs elements by having the corresponding references. Each SMD Data Services module can only be accessed by the elements in the same SMD or by the E2E SMD, avoiding the possibility that SMDs may affect other SMDs.

2.1.3. Physical Infrastructure

The third and lowest layer in the architecture presented is the physical infrastructure with multiple SMDs (i.e., edge/RAN, transport and cloud) and their available resources (i.e., optical network, computing and other resources) where the slice-subnets are deployed and monitored. The architecture presented aims to be technology independent, leaving this aspect to the Network Slice

Mngr/MANO as it is the latest element before reaching the technology-dependent controllers such as optical and packet-based networks for transport domains or virtual machine and cloud-native computing resources for core and edge domains.

2.2. Deployment of Secured Multi-domain Network Slices

As illustrated in Fig.2, the process to implement a secured E2E network slice is composed of four main phases: a) the E2E Network Slice & QoS selection and definition, b) the Domain Network Slice Deployment, c) the Setting Monitoring Rules and d) the Deployment Confirmation.

The whole workflow begins with a request from a tenant (1) specifying both the E2E NST to generate the E2E NSI and the SSLA requirements to be applied on the E2E SMD. The E2E SSLA Mngr receives the request, it retrieves the SSLA information and forwards it together with the selected NST identifier to the E2E Network Slice Mngr (2). The E2E Network Slice Mngr processes the request to generate the E2E NSI object, which allows to keep track of the Network Slicing resources being used in each SMD and, finally, it generates a MSPL object for the E2E SO (3 and 4) This is the only MSPL generated by the Network Slice Manager because it is closely related to the requested NST and so, the MSPL is generated the the request arrived to the Network Slice Manager. Any other policy action is managed between the E2E SO and the E2E PF. The E2E SO, proceeds to generate an E2E security orchestration plan to fulfill the correct E2E NST deployment (5).

At this point, the second phase starts with the E2E SO translates the received MSPL into the set of different new MSPLs to be sent towards the involved domain SOs to deploy the multiple domain network slices, also called E2E network slice subnets (6 and 7). At this point a remark is necessary about the relationship between the E2E PF and the E2E SO; previously, it was described that the PF assists the SO in terms of policy conflicts, because Network Slices are thought to be isolated elements, deploying a new Network Slice should not generate any conflict. Then, if a new MSPLs needs to be applied on a deployed Network Slice and there might be a conflict to be studied is a different action later described. Moreover, as marked in the workflow with the note "A", from this moment all the domains involved apply the same actions. Once each domain SO receives the policy to deploy the slice-subnet, it generates a domain security orchestration plan (8) to manage the SMD slice-subnet and SSLA deployment. Once the plan is

ready, it forwards the corresponding request to the domain Network Slice Mngr/MANO element (9) to deploy the corresponding slice-subnet (i.e., a domain NSI based on a domain NST) (10) and it receives its confirmation (11).

Once the slice-subnet in a domain is deployed and its information stored in the E2E NSI, the SO triggers (12) the process to configure the monitoring based on the corresponding policy. As the monitoring is being configured, the DE needs to agree with the AE/DC which data is going to be used for the monitoring and decisions, for this reason the DE requests to the AE/DC to select the best algorithm to collect and process the monitored data based on the SSLA metrics that need to be monitored associated to the deployed slice-subnet resources (13). The AE/DC confirms the correct configuration (14) and, finally, the DE does the same to the SO (15). It is important to remark that, despite having the slice deployed, its metrics are not monitored until step 11 is applied. From that moment on the SSLA is evaluated constantly.

Finally, for each ready domain (i.e., slice-subnet deployed and SSLA configured), the single-domain SOs inform the E2E SO (16) which afterwards informs the E2E Network Slice Mngr (17). These last two elements update their own data objects with the latest information coming from the multiple involved SMDs (first the E2E SO and then the E2E Network Slice Mngr. and based on the status of the multiple deployed resources, the tenant is informed whether the secured E2E Network slice is ready and being monitored (note C).

2.3. Monitoring Secured Multi-domain Network Slices

With the secured E2E network slice ready to be used by the users, the services composing the network slice can be monitored to evaluate whether the SSLA has been violated or not and to apply the best solution possible based on the policies available. This whole process is presented in Fig.3 and it is composed of two main phases: a) the SSLA metrics Gathering & Evaluation and b) the SSLA Violation Management.

This process begins when a set of monitored data is received (1), processed (i.e., grouped in sets of data based on the previously defined metrics) and forwarded to the DE (2). The DE evaluates the received data and decides if an SSLA has been violated or not (3). If no violation has occurred, no other action is required and new monitored data are expected.

In case there is an SSLA violation, the DE retrieves the possible policies from the domain PF to fix the SSLA violation (4), the DE decides which one to apply, informs the SO about the policy (5) and the SO re-

Figure 2: Secure E2E network slice deployment.

requests the corresponding actions to the Network Slice Mngr/MANO (6), so this last one controls and manages the actions over the deployed slice-subnet (7). In parallel, the SO forwards the policy decided by the DE to the E2E SO (8). At this point, if the E2E SO evaluates that the SSLA resolution needs to be applied in another domain, it obtains the E2E policies from the E2E PF (9) and informs the corresponding domain SOs (10), which must orchestrate within their SMDs the necessary actions to enforce the policy received from the E2E SO.

2.4. Data Objects

Together with the multiple modules and their functionalities and how they relate to one another within both processes, one more key element needs to be kept in mind: the data objects generated and exchanged between modules to ensure the correct deployment and monitoring actions enforcement. While all domains (i.e., E2E, edge, Transport, core, etc.) in the architecture presented in Fig.1 had a Data Services module, this module was omitted in the workflows description of Figs.2 and 3 to avoid constant retrieval actions (i.e., getting or storing the data objects). This fact does not reduce the importance of having a well-defined data objects for each specific used element, for this reason

Figure 3: Secure E2E network slice monitoring.

an introduction to the data objects designed and implemented is done in this subsection.

2.4.1. E2E and Domain network slice Templates & Instances

As Network Slicing functionalities were designed at both levels (i.e., E2E and domain), the idea was to generate a data object structure that could be used in both layers in order to keep the maximum possible homogeneity and a correlation between the E2E and the domain network slice Managers. As presented by the GSMA since its initial Network Slicing reports to the latest [14], the idea was to generate a generic NST. Due to the complexity of the architecture presented in our initial implementations, the NST (Listing 1) was kept as simple as possible with the most essential metadata (i.e., id, name, description, etc.), the list of slice-subnets

(i.e., a reference to a domain NST id, location of that NST, etc.) and how the slice-subnets were linked. At the domain level, the same structure was used but the slice-subnets items had the reference to the NSs and their VNFs composing the NST in that domain.

Once a NST is deployed, the generated NSI is based on the NST itself and it includes the references to the instantiated elements together with the SSLA reference.

2.4.2. Security SLAs

Regarding the SSLA data object used in our system, a machine readable format was adopted based on the SPECS SSLA model [15] and extended to support Network Slicing. Keeping this in mind, a generic example is presented in (Listing 2) in which, apart from the essential metadata (i.e., id, name, etc.), there are three

```

{
  "id": "nst_uuid",
  "name": "nst_name",
  "description": "nst_description",
  "slice-subnets": [
    {
      "id-ref": "subnet_id",
      "name": "subnet_name",
      "location": "domain_id"
    }
  ],
  "virtual-links": [
    {...}
  ]
}

```

Listing 1: NST structure example

main blocks:

- slice-resources: it contains the list of available E2E NSTs that can be deployed and monitored using the SSLA.
- security-capabilities: A capability is a set of security controls and each security control is an implementation of one or more specific security mechanisms, that also may be monitored if associated metrics are part of SLOs (see below) to be monitored. Well-known examples of security controls are those defined by the NIST's Control Framework [16].
- metrics: this third element is referenced in the E2E NSI and the domain NSIs in order to define the different Security Service Level Objectives (SLOs) to be monitored and to verify the compliance with the SSLA. Each metric element contains its definition and its measurement scale among other properties for the monitoring configuration process.

2.4.3. Policies

While the previous two data objects were defined for specific concepts (i.e., SSLA, network slice), the idea of policy in the architecture designed has a wider vision. A policy is used to define an action to be managed by the E2E SO, the domain SO or even the DE modules.

Within the context of the architecture presented, a policy (Listing 3) was designed to define two types of actions: a) "Deployment" to manage the secured (E2E

```

{
  "id": "ssla_uuid",
  "name": "ssla_name",
  "description": "ssla_description",
  "slice-resources": [
    {
      "nst-ref": "nst_uuid"
    },
    {...}
  ],
  "security-capabilities": [
    {
      "id": "capability_id",
      "description": "cap_desc",
      "security-controls": [...]
    },
    {...}
  ],
  "metrics": [
    {
      "id": "metric_id",
      "service-level-objectives": {...}
    },
    {...}
  ]
}

```

Listing 2: SSLA structure example

and domain) network slices and b) "Configuration" to prepare the monitoring elements based on the selected SSLA and to apply corrections after an SSLA violation is detected. In both cases, the necessary information to manage all the elements is presented through the "nst-ref" and "ssla-requirements" fields, allowing to define a single policy structure for the whole infrastructure and domain independent.

3. Experimental Validation

Based on all the previously described architecture, this section aims to present an agile proof of concept to demonstrate the deployment and monitoring functionalities through the implementation of a DoS attack scenario.

3.1. A DoS Use Case

In order to evaluate the architecture described in the previous section, a simulated multi-domain environ-

```

{
  "id": "policy-instance-uuid",
  "subnet-name": "E2ENSI-name_SMD",
  "nst-ref": "nst_uuid",
  "location": "domain_id",
  "type": "DEPLOYMENT/CONFIGURATION",
  "status": "status",
  "ssla-requirements": [
    {
      "metric": "metric_id",
      "slo": {...}
    },
    {...}
  ]
}

```

Listing 3: Policy structure example

ment was created and is illustrated in Fig.4. The developed simulation was composed of the following domains: an edge SMD, a core SMD (with the transport and core physical infrastructures) and finally, the E2E SMD. The E2E network slice contains a generic server (i.e., a receiver of requests with no specific functionality) in the core domain with a firewall service placed on the edge and both domains interconnected through a transport domain. The firewall is placed in the edge SMD with the idea to protect both the service in the core SMD and the traffic in the transport domain because the increment of traffic may cause unexpected issues such as light power anomalies or a bandwidth increment. The services were defined using two different NSTs, each deployed by the corresponding domain Network Slice Mngr/MANO (and the VIMs and WIM below) to compose the E2E network slice element.

Since each fiber carries an enormous amount of data traffic, even a brief disruption of services may result in disastrous consequences.

Together with the E2E NST, an E2E SSLA was selected defining a threshold for the number of requests coming from a single user in order to avoid that a DoS could take all the bandwidth assigned in the connectivity service and block the generic server functionality. As the scope of this article is the security management of an E2E network slice and its SSLA monitoring but not the DoS itself (there are attacks of Tbps [17]), a simple DoS attack version was designed with an SSLA metric that defined a maximum number of requests per minute and user with an SLO of 30 requests/minute.

Figure 4: DoS use case design.

3.2. Results

The first set of results is the validation of the main actions described in subsections 2.2 and 2.3 which are illustrated in Fig.5 and Fig.6 with the different Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) requests done among the different modules. Regarding the deployment procedure, evaluating Fig.5, the four main phases defined in the original workflow can be identified. The "E2E Network Slice & QoS Selection and Definition" with the first three requests, then the "Domain Network Slice Deployment" with the requests 4,5,6,7,8 and 11. The third phase called "Setting Monitoring Rules" started first in the edge domain with the requests 9 and 10 and in the core domain with the request 12 and 14. Finally, the fourth and last phase called "Deployment Confirmation" is done with the requests 13, 15,16 and 17. On the other side, while the users made use of the service (requests 1 and 3), the monitoring process in Fig.6 shows its two main phases. First, the "SSLA Metrics Gathering & Evaluation" phase with the requests 2 and 4 where the monitored data is gathered and sent to the DE so it establishes whether any metric defined by the SSLA is not respected and so, if the SSLA is violated. In case of a violation, the second phase "SSLA Violation Management" is applied with the HTTP requests 5,6,7,8,9 and 10. Meanwhile, all this process is transparent for the non-malicious user who kept requesting with a normal behaviour the offered service.

In addition to the presented HTTP traffic among the system modules, Fig.7 shows the time evolution and resolution of the DoS attack scenario. First, as both graphs show, the two users send the same amount of requests (i.e., 6 requests/minute) to the generic server (through the Firewall) but when the malicious user (orange line) decides to attack (minute 12:50), an increment of re-

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Info
0.000000000	Tenant	E2E SSLA Mngnr.	HTTP	POST /e2e_sla/deploy_slice_sla HTTP/1.1
0.000007697	EZE SSLA Mngnr.	E2E Network Slice Mngnr.	HTTP/JSON	POST /e2e_slicer/instance/deploy HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
0.012136175	EZE Network Slice Mngnr.	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /e2e_so/policies HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
0.015534926	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	EDGE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /so/policies HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
0.018943316	EDGE Sec. Orchestrator	EDGE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	HTTP/JSON	POST /slicer/instance/deploy HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
0.026083696	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	CORE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /so/policies HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
0.029357459	CORE Sec. Orchestrator	CORE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	HTTP/JSON	POST /slicer/instance/deploy HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.033412139	EDGE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	EDGE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /so/policies/e14d7886-bf40-487b-841a-211c1000f227 HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.037173338	EDGE Sec. Orchestrator	EDGE Decision Engine	HTTP/JSON	POST /de/monitoring_rules HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.041952866	EDGE Decision Engine	EDGE Analytics Engine & Data Collector	HTTP/JSON	POST /ae/metrics HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.044195455	CORE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	CORE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /so/policies/8ada5fbb-f636-4312-bd7c-a71322b8431e HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.048151976	CORE Sec. Orchestrator	CORE Decision Engine	HTTP/JSON	POST /de/monitoring_rules HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.049842663	EDGE Sec. Orchestrator	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /e2e_so/policies/e14d7886-bf40-487b-841a-211c1000f227 HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.052059902	CORE Decision Engine	CORE Analytics Engine & Data Collector	HTTP/JSON	POST /ae/metrics HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.054735470	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	EZE Network Slice Mngnr.	HTTP/JSON	POST /e2e_slicer/instance/policy-update/e14d7886-bf40-487b-841a-211c1000f227 HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.059838774	CORE Sec. Orchestrator	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /e2e_so/policies/8ada5fbb-f636-4312-bd7c-a71322b8431e HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
10.064186699	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	EZE Network Slice Mngnr.	HTTP/JSON	POST /e2e_slicer/instance/policy-update/8ada5fbb-f636-4312-bd7c-a71322b8431e HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)

Figure 5: Wireshark capture with the Secure E2E network slice deployment actions.

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Info
1 74.436641694	User	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	HTTP/JSON	POST /fw/pings HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
2 74.440599743	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	EDGE Analytics Engine & Data Collector	HTTP/JSON	POST /ae/metrics/data HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
3 74.445688179	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	WebServer-subnet (CORE)	HTTP/JSON	POST /web/pings HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
4 75.10252550	EDGE Analytics Engine & Data Collector	EDGE Decision Engine	HTTP/JSON	POST /de/collected_data HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
5 75.108727153	EDGE Decision Engine	EDGE Policy Framework	HTTP	GET /pf/get_policies/dos HTTP/1.1
6 75.114059354	EDGE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	EDGE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	HTTP/JSON	POST /slicer/instance/update_config HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
7 75.119125266	EDGE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	HTTP/JSON	POST /fw/config HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
8 75.121701576	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	EDGE Network Slice Mngnr./MANO	HTTP/JSON	HTTP/1.0 200 OK, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
9 75.126535746	EDGE Decision Engine	EDGE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP	POST /so/policies/security_notification HTTP/1.1
10 75.131538521	EDGE Sec. Orchestrator	EZE Sec. Orchestrator	HTTP/JSON	POST /e2e_so/policies/security_notification HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
11 75.455631807	User	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	HTTP/JSON	POST /fw/pings HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
12 82.853536088	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	EDGE Analytics Engine & Data Collector	HTTP/JSON	POST /ae/metrics/data HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
13 82.858972156	FireWall-subnet (EDGE)	WebServer-subnet (CORE)	HTTP/JSON	POST /web/pings HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)

Figure 6: Wireshark capture with the Secure E2E network slice monitoring actions.

quests can be seen on the left graph passing from 6 requests/minute to 60 requests/minute (an increment of 10) with the main objective to block the performance of the service. As previously defined, the SLO was a maximum amount of 30. So, when this threshold was not respected, the monitoring system reacted and applied the procedure defined and demonstrated in Figs.3 and 6. This resulted on the resolution of the DoS attack as it can be seen in the right graph of Fig.7 with the traffic from the malicious user reaching a peak of 60 requests/minute but suddenly decreasing to 0 requests/minute and absolute blockage of its traffic.

A third set of results showing the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) with the probability that the DoS detection and resolution processes last less than X seconds are illustrated in Figs. 8 and 9. Checking both figures, the detection of the DoS done by the security monitoring system has an 80% of probability to be detected in less than 82s; whereas the resolution action is implemented with a very low time, giving a 100% probability to require less than 0.4s to solve the thread. After conducting all the tests, the detection mean time obtained was of 49.5728s with a standard deviation of 20.07s. On the resolution time side, its mean value was of 0.0463s with a standard deviation of 0.1005s. The reason why the mean time is around 50s is because at the design time of the use case, it was planned to work in the range of a minute (i.e., 30requests/minute) rather than seconds. Despite this aspect is out of the scope of this article, the detection could (and should) be improved as there are works [18] dealing with more complex DoS attack (i.e., Distributed DoS) in less time.

Finally, based on the obtained results, the theoretical architecture description done in 2 has been validated from different points of view such as: a) the processes to deploy and monitor a secured E2E network slice, b) the correct functionality of the deployed service and, finally, c) the needs in terms of time for the monitoring system to reach and solve a thread/attack situation. The implementation of the architecture worked as expected, with the designed data objects allowing the correct track of the information during each step of the designed deployment and monitoring processes. Moreover, as the DoS use case worked as desired with each slice-subnet deployed in the appropriate domain and then, with the right monitoring actions being performed, the architecture has been validated.

4. Conclusions

This article aimed to be one of the first works to associate E2E network slices management with specific security monitoring system. While multiple works have been presented in the last years involving Network Slicing and security-related aspects such as how to isolate the complete network slice or one of its slice-subnets (e.g., using an optical fiber per service), but the existence of works focusing on a complete security-specific system for multi-domain E2E network slices is not very extensive, which is where this article aims to contribute.

The set of elements composing the whole monitoring infrastructure were presented for the E2E domain and the domains below (i.e., transport and computing) together with the description of how the two main actions

Figure 7: Data flows received by the Firewall (left) and the generic server (right).

Figure 8: DoS Detection Time CDF.

Figure 9: DoS (SSLA Violation) Resolution Time CDF.

(i.e., deployment and monitoring) should work. In addition, a set of validation and experimental results using a DoS to block the transport connectivity towards a service in the core domain were described to demonstrate the correct performance of the system and to prove that the described architecture may be an interesting reference for other future works on the relationship between SSLAs and network slices.

While Network Slicing is a technology with already some years of life, its study and research possibilities are still far away from reaching the end. In fact, in the next generation of networks (i.e., beyond 5G and 6G)

their security is one of the key aspects, for example the isolation is expected to be studied from three different points of view (i.e., performance, management and security) or an improvement of its management and orchestration with better automated processes or the inclusion of revolutionary technologies such as Artificial Intelligence or Distributed Ledger Technologies. Regarding the work presented in this article, the design of more complex scenarios such as designing more constrained SSLAs and complex network slices are other paths to follow in order to improve the performance of the architecture presented before it can be planned to move towards a real-world scenario.

Acknowledgment

This work is partially funded by the EC through the EC/5GPPP INSPIRE-5GPlus (871808) project and the "Grant RTI2018-099178-B-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF A way of making Europe".

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